

КУЛЬТУРНО-ИСТОРИЧЕСКОЕ НАСЛЕДИЕ КРЫМСКОГО РЕГИОНА НА «ВЕЛИКОМ ШЕЛКОВОМ ПУТИ» КАК ОСНОВА ДЛЯ МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОГО ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ И ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ

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Аннотация. В статье определено, что этнокультурная идентичность определяется как составная часть социальной идентичности личности, которая относится к этнокультурному самосознанию своей вовлеченности в этнокультурную группу. Этнокультурная идентичность имеет два основных изменения: вовлеченность и этнокультурное самосознание. Таким образом отмечена особенность сознания индивида при определении собственной тождественности – субъективно-символический аспект.

В работе приведен пример многовековой толерантности в крымском регионе и продолжение этих традиций. Выявлена роль культурно-исторического наследия крымского региона на «Великом шелковом пути».

Отмечено, что сохранение историко-культурного наследия и развитие познавательного туризма способствуют развитию межкультурного взаимодействия. А для того, чтобы поддерживать принципы толерантности народов необходима согласованная и целенаправленная работа ряда государственных структур, образовательных, историко-культурных общественных и религиозных организаций.

Ключевые слова: культурно-историческое наследие, межкультурное взаимодействие, мультикультурное общество, поликультурное общество, толерантность.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada etnomadaniy o'ziga xoslik shaxsning ijtimoiy o'ziga xosligining ajralmas qismi sifatida ta'riflanishi, bu shaxsning etnomadaniy guruhga daxldorligining etnikmadaniy o'zini o'zi anglashini anglatadi. Etnomadaniy o'ziga xoslik ikkita asosiy o'zgarishga ega: ishtirok etish va etnikmadaniy o'zini o'zi anglash. Shunday qilib, o'z shaxsiyatini aniqlashda shaxs ongining o'ziga xos xususiyati - sub'ektiv-ramziy jihat qayd etiladi.

Asarda Qrim mintaqasida ko'p asrlik bag'rikenglik va bu an'analarning davom etishi namunasi keltirilgan. Qrim mintaqasining madaniy va tarixiy merosining "Buyuk ipak yo'li"dagi o'rni ochib berildi.

Qayd etilishicha, tarixiy-madaniy merosni asrab-avaylash va ta'lim turizmini rivojlantirish madaniyatlararo hamkorlikni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi. Xalqlar o'rtasida bag'rikenglik tamoyillarini qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida bir qator davlat organlari, ta'lim, tarixiy-madaniy, jamoat va diniy tashkilotlarning kelishilgan va maqsadli ish olib borishi zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniy va tarixiy meros, madaniyatlararo o'zaro ta'sir, ko'p madaniyatli jamiyat, ko'p madaniyatli jamiyat, bag'rikenglik.

Abstract. The article determines that ethnocultural identity is defined as an integral part of a person's social identity, which refers to the ethnocultural self-awareness of one's involvement in an ethnocultural group. Ethnocultural identity has two main changes: involvement and ethnocultural self-awareness. Thus, a feature of the individual's consciousness when determining his own identity is noted - the subjective-symbolic aspect.

The work provides an example of centuries-old tolerance in the Crimean region and the continuation of these traditions. The role of the cultural and historical heritage of the Crimean region on the "Great Silk Road" is revealed.

It is noted that the preservation of historical and cultural heritage and the development of educational tourism contribute to the development of intercultural interaction. And in order to support the principles of tolerance among peoples, coordinated and purposeful work of a number of government agencies, educational, historical, cultural, public and religious organizations is necessary.

Keywords: *cultural and historical heritage, intercultural interaction, multicultural society, multicultural society, tolerance.*

Introduction. The specificity of modern social existence is the diversity of all aspects of its existence - sociocultural structures, ways of life, socio-political conditions, etc. In these conditions, intolerance has become one of the global problems. Its essence lies in the denial and suppression of differences between individuals and cultures. Society can only counteract these phenomena with tolerance. Modern social consciousness formalizes the idea of tolerance as a moral quality that characterizes the acceptance by one individual or society of the interests, convictions, beliefs, and habits of other people or communities. Lack of tolerance breeds hatred. Hatred leads to mistrust. Distrust entails people's distance from each other. Tolerance allows people of different backgrounds, religions and beliefs to work and live together, and this leads to greater work efficiency and creates team unity. Where there is discrimination, there cannot be peace and peaceful coexistence. Lack of tolerance leads to conflicts and instability in people's relationships and their work.

Tolerance expresses the human desire to achieve mutual understanding and coordination of a variety of motives, attitudes, and orientations. At the same time, the relationship between people of different ethnic cultures should occur without resorting to violence or suppression of human dignity, but using humanitarian opportunities - dialogue, clarification, cooperation. Cultural and educational tourism can become the basis for such intercultural dialogue.

Main Part. Tolerance is the art of living in a world of different people and ideas, the ability to have equal rights and freedoms, without violating the rights and freedoms of other people. At the same time, tolerance is not a concession, condescension or indulgence, but an active life position based on the recognition of something different [6].

The concept of "multicultural society" seems to emphasize not the multiplicity of coexisting cultures (which have formed into a kind of multicultural space), but the multiple repetition and replication of cultural differences. By supporting the policy of multicultural diversity, the ideology of multiculturalism develops the limits of acceptable diversity, replicates acceptable differences and disseminates them [7].

Yu.V. Stavropolsky proposes to combine the concepts of ethnic and cultural identity. Ethnocultural identity is defined as an integral part of a person's social identity, which refers to the ethnocultural self-awareness of one's involvement in an ethnocultural group. Ethnocultural identity has two main changes: involvement and ethnocultural self-awareness." That is, the author turns specifically to the consciousness of the individual when determining his own identity - the subjective-symbolic aspect. Let us point out that the author in his works uses the term exclusively "multicultural" society [8].

The new paradigm of multicultural development is characterized by a number of new phenomena. Firstly, there is a change in the world of cultural transmission, which was carried out mainly through special activities in the conditions of specially organized institutions, through the increasing role of other types of cultural translators not previously used for this (subcultures, the Internet, mass media, means of art: music, cinema, video, etc.).

Secondly, new subjects of broadcasting activities are appearing in the cultural and educational space: large corporations, non-profit and public organizations, nature reserves, tourist sites, museums, hotels, shops, etc., which through various types of their activities act as cultural broadcasters, including the younger generation in these processes.

Thirdly, the educational space is expanding, previously limited to cultural, educational and educational institutions, new subjects of educational activity, competing with traditional educational institutions.

The unique symbiosis of elements of different cultures, coexisting different ethnocultural traditions gave rise to a number of features inherent in Russian civilization and played a significant role throughout a number of socio-historical formations. This feature, first of all, is tolerance.

Let's consider how a multicultural society developed in the Crimean region, which was part of the Great Silk Road.

Numerous historical sources indicate that merchant caravans with a wide variety of goods from the beaten path of the "Great Silk Road" headed in the Middle Ages to the shores of the Black Sea, stopping at the caravanserais of Solkhat (Old Crimea), Kafa (Feodosia), Soldaya (Sudak) and until a certain time Kherson (Chersonese). There is evidence of this from contemporaries. The Pope's ambassador to the Mongol Kagan, Guillaume Rubruk, who visited Crimea in 1253, describes the trade turnover of Soldaya (Sudak): "All the merchants come there, both those traveling from Turkey and wanting to head to the northern countries, and those traveling back from Russia and the northern countries ... Some bring stoats, squirrels and other precious furs; others bring cotton fabrics, cotton paper, silk fabrics and fragrant roots... Merchants from Constantinople send their boats to buy dried fish, namely sturgeon, chebak and others in unlimited quantities" [9].

In Russian cultural history, Crimea represents the most striking example of the interaction of cultures; it is the focus of a huge cultural heritage, centuries-old cultural traditions and inexhaustible creative potential.

The research allowed us to note the historical and cultural finds of the ancient peoples of the peninsula, described below [based on information 1-3].

Archaeologists have discovered many sites of ancient people from the Paleolithic, Mesolithic, Neolithic, Copper and Bronze Ages, in the steppe and mountainous Crimea, on the southern coast and the Kerch Peninsula. On the territory of Crimea and the federal city of Sevastopol there are four sites of ancient people dating from 1.5 million to 10 thousand years BC. e., classified as objects of cultural heritage of federal significance: archaeological complex on the Ak-Kaya plateau, Belogorsky district, cave site Murzak-Koba near the village of Chernorechenskoye, Balaklava region, cave sites Fatma-Koba and Shan-Koba near the village of Peredovoe, Balaklava region. In the steppe, mountainous Crimea and on the Kerch Peninsula, mounds from the Copper Age, copper tools and weapons were found: axes, daggers, knives, chisels, paper clips, spear and arrowheads, bones of domestic animals.

To objects of cultural heritage of federal significance in Crimea from the 2nd millennium to the 10th century. BC e., include: the archaeological complex on the Ak-Kaya plateau of the

Belogorsk region, the settlement "Kamenka" near Kerch and the archaeological complex "Karaul-Oba" near the village of Veseloye and the village of Novy Svet in the urban district of Sudak.

The old name of Crimea - Taurida - is associated with the Tauri tribes that inhabited the mountainous part and southern coast of Crimea from Cape Aya to Feodosia since the early Iron Age, which includes the first archaeological monuments of this people on the peninsula.

There are many Taurus monuments known in Crimea: settlements dating back to the 9th–6th centuries. BC e., found near Inkerman, near the village of Partizanskoye, not far from Bakhchisarai, near the village of Krasnopeshernoye not far from Simferopol. Balaklava and Belogorskoe; settlements of the 6th–5th centuries. BC e. found on Mount Koshka near Simeiz, near the village of Novy Svet, in the Kosh-Koba cave near the villages of Lesnoye, Krasnogorskoye, Simferopolskoye, in caves in the Baydar Valley, in the coastal regions of the Kerch Peninsula; V–I centuries BC e. on Cape Ai-Todor in the Gaspra region, on Mount AyuDag in the Gurzuf region, on Mount Krestovaya in the Alupka Valley, on Mount Kastel near Alushta, in Osipova Balka and near the village of Zavetnoye near Bakhchisaray, in the village of Aivazovskoye, between the villages of Zalesnoye and Krepkoye.

Cimmerian culture in Crimea is represented in eastern and southeastern Crimea. In the east, about ten burials dating from the 8th – early 7th centuries are known. BC e., in the southeast the main archaeological monuments of the Cimmerians are located: burial grounds near Kerch, Zeleny Yar, near the villages of Lugovoe and Frontovoye.

In Crimea, Scythian culture is represented by numerous burials starting from the 7th century. The oldest burial grounds date back to the 7th century. BC e. – a burial ground on Mount Temir near Kerch and a mound near the village of Filatovka, Krasnoperekopsk district.

In the 7th century BC e. The ancient Greeks first came to Crimea, cultural ties and trade relations began to develop between the population of Crimea and the Ionian Greeks, evidence of which is a skillfully painted vase found in a Scythian burial ground on Mount Temir.

Around 480 BC e. The Greek city-states of Eastern Crimea united into a single Bosphoran kingdom.

The appearance of the Sarmatians in Crimea dates back to the second half of the 1st - beginning of the 2nd centuries. BC e., the migration of the tribes was peaceful - there is no evidence of destruction in the archaeological monuments of this period. Sugdeya is modern Sudak, which was an observation post and pier - the main port of the Alans in Crimea.

In the 1st century n. e. At the request of Chersonese, the main base of the Romans in Crimea, Roman troops arrived in Crimea to protect against attacks by the Scythians and Alans. The Romans defeated the Scythian-Sarmatian detachments, controlled Chersonesos and the surrounding area, the entire southern coast of Crimea to Sudak, and the Bosphoran kingdom. The largest Roman fortress in Crimea, a cultural heritage site of federal significance - Charax, was built on Cape Ai-Todor near the modern village of Gaspra in the Yalta region during the period of the Romans' constant presence in Crimea in the 1st century. n. e. Another Roman camp was set up in Simbolon Bay near Balaklava.

On the territory of the Republic of Crimea and the federal city of Sevastopol there are many objects of cultural heritage of federal significance from the Iron Age era and ancient civilizations (Appendix 1). Among the particularly valuable objects of cultural heritage, included in the list of UNESCO World Heritage Sites, is the State Historical and Archaeological Museum-Reserve "Tavrichesky Chersonese" in Sevastopol. The cultural influence of Byzantium and the spread of Christianity in Crimea played a decisive role in the unification and mixing of all tribes.

Since then, many nationalities have lived in different periods on the territory of Crimea, leaving their traces in historical and cultural objects. Historically established ethnocultural and religious diversity is a special characteristic of Crimean society. Let us consider the ethnic composition of Crimea based on the results of the 2014 population census: Russians (1189 thousand people), Ukrainians (291,6 thousand people), Crimean Tatars (229,5 thousand people), Belarusians (17,9 thousand people), Azerbaijanis (4.4 thousand people), Uzbeks (3.5 thousand people), Moldovans (3.1 thousand people), as well as Jews, Koreans, Greeks, Poles, Gypsies, Chuvashs, Bulgarians, Germans, Mordovians, Georgians, Turks, Tajiks, Maris, Bashkirs, Udmurts, Ossetians, Kazakhs, Arabs, Karaites, Krymchaks [4].

Of course, the development of historical and cultural tourism in the region has influenced the preservation and enhancement of attractive historical and cultural sites. Many people are trying to destroy the phenomenon of multiculturalism, but the state is taking all possible measures to stabilize it.

Thus, in the Crimean region, tasks to strengthen interethnic harmony and meet the cultural and educational needs of national minorities are being gradually carried out. Three state languages were proclaimed: Russian, Ukrainian and Crimean Tatar.

A law was adopted on the rehabilitation of previously deported peoples: Germans, Bulgarians, Greeks, Armenians and Crimean Tatars. Eid al-Adha and Kurban Bayram have been declared national holidays.

Social and cultural events play a huge role in this: publications of fiction and educational literature are financed; the material base of national schools, creative groups, museums, libraries, medical centers, etc. is being strengthened.

The most important aspect of ensuring the rights of national minorities is the development of education in native languages and the revival of national cultures [5].

The study of the native language is organized in general educational institutions and on the basis of national-cultural societies: more than 120 people study the Armenian language; Bulgarian - 77; Hebrew - 22; German - 78 and optional - 39; Korean - 20; Estonian - 27; modern Greek - 91, optional - 210; Polish - 45, etc. [10].

Particular attention is paid to the revival and development of national cultures, support of folk and exemplary creative groups. Currently, there are 91 Crimean Tatar groups, 89 Ukrainian and 81 Russian groups. There are Greek, German, Belarusian, Armenian, Bulgarian, Karaite and other creative groups. The "House of Friendship" was created.

The republican local history, art and ethnographic museums, city and regional museums constantly operate exhibitions dedicated to the culture and history of the national minorities of the peninsula. Work is underway to restore and preserve monuments and landmarks of the history and culture of the peoples of Crimea [10-11].

Conclusion. Thus, the principle of tolerance in interethnic relations is the norm of relations between citizens of Crimea. And this instills a respectful attitude towards the historical past of the peninsula, the history of its ethnic groups, their customs and traditions, way of life, culture, etc. Thus, the symbiosis of cultures and the unity of patriotic education, as well as the development of cultural and historical tourism, make it possible to strengthen tolerance in relations between peoples living in the Republic of Crimea.

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